

CONTACT FORCE MEASUREMENT AND DELAMINATING RESPONSES OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE SUBJECTED TO SMALL- MASS IMPACT

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Keywords: Composite plates, Impact, Small mass, Contact force

ABSTRACT

The finite element method is used to establish a 3D model of composite laminates and a deformable impactor. The cohesive element is employed to simulate the delamination onset and growth. The dropping weight impact is simulated to validate the model. Both of the delamination size and delamination threshold load from finite element simulation are in good agreement with the test result. A sudden drop of load occurs on the delamination initiating. The simulation of small mass impact show that the slope of contact force becomes lower after the delamination onset. The strain of impactor is utilized to calculate the contact force, which is interfered by the longitudinal vibration of the impactor. The filtered contact force time history matches with the real one, and a spike is observed from it on the delamination occurring. The velocity of the opposite of impacted site also shows fluctuations corresponding to the delamination occurring, while the strain and displacement responses do not show this feature. The simulation with impactor arm demonstrates that the stiffness and mass affect the contact force under the same impact velocity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite material such as carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminate are widely used in aircraft structures. But the laminate is very sensitive to the transvers load most of which are caused by the impact due to falling weight, debris and ice hail, etc. The impact load may create the internal delamination in the laminate which is undetectable by vision inspection. The delamination reduces the flexural stiffness of laminates which may lead to the premature buckling failure^{[1],[2]}. Hence, the impact damage is a primary issue for composite structure design. The delamination threshold load (DTL) is one of critical parameters for the damage resistance metric^[3]. In the low velocity impact test, the DTL is the value of the time-load or displacement-load curves where a sudden load drop occurs as a result of the loss of flexural rigidity due to delamination growth^[4].

The dropping weight impact generally represents the quasi static impact caused by the impactor with a larger mass. It is easy to mount the sensor on the impactor head. The small mass impact due to runway debris^[5] and ice hail^[6] also create the laminate damage. The small mass has a weight from a few grams to dozens of grams. It is difficult to install a sensor on the impactor. The acceleration of impactor can be measured with the digital image correlation technique^[7], and then is used to compute

the contact force. The dynamical strain response of the impactor can also be used to obtain the contact force^[8], but the identification of event of delamination is still to be studied. In this work, the simulation of small mass impact on the laminate is conducted. The responses of impactor and plate are investigated to found the delamination event.

2 FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

2.1 Validation of Simulation Method

To simulate the response of laminate under small mass impact, the finite element (FE) model is setup with ABAQUS/Explicit. The specimen is carbon epoxy laminate, with plies of 0.188mm and layup of $[0/45/90/-45]_4$. The mechanical properties of the tape are shown in Table 1. Each layer is modelled with the linear hexahedron element (C3D8R in ABAQUS). The interface between layers is represented by cohesive elements (COH3D8), sharing nodes with the matching C3D8R meshes. The cohesive element has thickness of zero and properties shown in Table 2.

E_{11}	127GPa
$E_{22}=E_{33}$	10 GPa
$G_{12}=G_{13}$	5.4 GPa
G_{23}	3.05 GPa
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.34
ν_{23}	0.36
density	1540kg/m ³

Table 1. Mechanical properties of tape

$E_{nn}=E_{ss}=E_{tt}$	1000 GPa
Shearing strength	64MPa
$G_{1c}=G_{2c}$	750J/m ²

Table 2. Material properties of cohesive element

Figure 1. FE model of the composite plate: (a) large mass impact and (b) small mass impact

The modeling is firstly validated with dropping weight impact test. The weight of impactor is 5.3kg, and the diameter to the head is 16mm. The specimen is a simply supported circular plate of 100mm diameter (Fig.1a). An impactor head is modeled with solid elements (C3D8R) and a lumped mass element is attached to the top of the head to represent the weight. The falling tower test was conducted on the same type of specimen, with an impact energy of 27J. The stress of impactor head is output to calculate the contact force which is compared with the measured one together the original output

contact force by the ABAQUS (Fig.2). The force from the stress is consist with the original one, and they are also close to the measured one. The delamination event is also presented in the simulation as well as the in the experimental result. The delamination regions from simulation and supersonic C-scan are shown in Fig.3, where the delamination sizes of them are also close. So that this model is valid for the response simulation of laminate under impact load.

Figure 2. Contact force time histories

Figure 3. Comparison of delamination region between experimental and FEM result: (a) C-scan and (b) simulation

2.2 Model for Small Mass Impact

A circular laminate with the diameter of 240mm and the layup of $[0/45/90/-45]_2$ is established (Fig.2b). According the study of Olsson[9], the small mass impact condition is that the mass of impactor is lower than 1/5 of that of impact affected region of the plate. The mass of affected region is give by

$$M_{affected} = \pi^2 t \sqrt{2mD^*} \quad (1)$$

where m is the mass per unit area of laminate; D^* is the effective flexural rigidity. For the above laminate $M_{affected}$ is 41g, which mean that the small mass condition is satisfied when the mass of impactor is lower than 8.2g.

Four aluminum impactors with a diameter of 12.7mm but the different mass are employed in this study (Fig.4). Because the mass of these models is enough to represent the small mass object, so no lumped mass element is created for them. The responses of impactor will used to obtain the contact

force to investigate the measurement method of experimental contact force. The contact force from the response of impactor is

$$F_c = Ma = \frac{M}{M_0} \sigma_3 S \tag{2}$$

where M is the mass of impactor, a is the acceleration of the impactor during the impact, M_0 is the mass above the location where the response is used to determine the contact force; σ_3 is the direct stress in the axial direction; S is the cross sectional area of the impactor.

Figure 4. Finite element model of impactor

2.3 Mode Analysis on Impactor

For the period of small mass impact on laminate is less than 10^{-3} s, the vibration of impactor may interfere the contact force. The vibrational mode of the impactor of 4.9g is analyzed (Table 3 and Fig.5). For there are six rigid body modes, the elastic mode starts from No.7.

Mode number	Mode shape	Modal frequency (Hz)
7	Twisting	1.16×10^5
8	Bending	1.33×10^5
9	Bending	1.33×10^5
10	Longitudinal	1.62×10^5

Table 3. Vibrational mode of the impactor

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Features of contact force

To investigate the contact force measurement, the impact without delamination is also simulated previously to that with delamination. The contact force of both models with and without delamination

are interfered by a signal with frequency of $1.63 \times 10^5 \text{ Hz}$ (Fig.6), which is resulted in the longitudinal vibration of the impactor. A low pass filtering is applied to the original contact force.

Figure 5. Vibrational mode shapes of impactor: (a)7th mode, (b)8th and 9th mode, and (c)10th mode

Figure 6. Contact force from strain responses (impactor:4.9g; impact velocity: 45m/s):
(a)With delamination and (b) Without delamination

The contact force from filtered strain responses is compared with that of contact surfaces in the FE software (Fig.7). The former is consist with the later one. The slope of contact force curve with delamination becomes lower than that with delamination upon a moment, on which the delamination damage is observed in the laminate model (Fig.8). The contact force from strain also shows different feature to that originally output by the software. A spike of is presented in the force curve obtained from the strain response of impactor, which represents the dramatic change of load exerted on the impactor.

3.2 Parametric analysis on contact force

The contact forces with and without delamination under the impact of different impactors are simulated (Fig.9). In Fig.9b, all of the contact force are calculated with the strain response of the impactor, and show the delamination event which is not shown in Fig.9a. The DTL of this plate is 1050N, so that the contact force with impactor mass of 4.9g and impact velocity of 20m/s is simulated to show the feature in the case that the peak of contact force is lower than the DTL.

Figure 7. Comparison of contact force

Figure 8. Delamination area of small mass impact

Figure 10. Contact force time histories under impactors of different mass: (a) without delamination and (b) with delamination

3.3 Features of other type of response

For some actual small mass impacts, such as that caused by ice hail, it is impossible to install a sensor on the impactor, so that it is necessary to find other responses to show the delamination event. The simulated results show that the velocity on the back of impacted site shows a spike due to the change of contact force (Fig.11).

Fig.11 Velocity time histories of impact site: (a)4.9g,45m/s and (b)1.5g, 45m/s

The displacement (Fig.12) and the strain (Fig.13) of the laminate are different for the cases with and without delamination, but the moment of delaminating is not shown by these two response. This is resulted in that the displacement of plate is always continuous in time domain therefore does not show the dramatic change of impact force that the plate is subjected to. The strain is consist with the displacement in time domain, so does not show the delaminating either.

Figure 12. Plate strain curve

Figure 13. Displacement curve of impacted site

4 IMPACT FORCE WITH ARM

In some small impact test, the impactor is driven by an arm rotating around a hinge. An impactor with an arm is modeled (Fig.14) to investigate the influence of arm on the contact force. The arm with a length of 295mm is assumed have a circular cross section. The impacting velocity is 15m/s. In Fig.15, the deviation of contact force increases with the arm radius. In the presented model, the impact force with arm of 1mm radius is absolutely acceptable.

Figure 14. Model of impactor with arm

Figure 15. Comparison of contact force

9 CONCLUSIONS

The vibration of small impactor may interfere the strain response of the impactor body. The true contact force is then obtained through low pass filtering on the strain response. The strain response of impactor body shows the delamination event, while the total force of the contact surface does not.

The fluctuation of velocity of impacted site also shows the occurring of delamination. The displacement and strain of the laminate changed after delaminating, but do not show the exact moment hence they is improper for DTL determination.

The property of arm of the apparatus for impact test affect the contact force. The stiffness and mass of the arm should be as low as possible for the impact test.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author thanks the support of Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant No. 11372192) and Natural Science Foundation of Shanghai, China (Grant No. 13ZR1422200).

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